

Polynuclear Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes with Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Salicylaldehyde

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Using Ni(SalH)₂ and Co(SalH)₂ as ligands, a few oxygen bridged complexes of calcium salts of deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and anthranilic acid are prepared. Similar alkaline metal complexes have been reported earlier¹.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing (5–6 h) a mixture of Ni(SalH)₂ or Co(SalH)₂ and calcium salts in the ratio of 1 : 1 in absolute ethanol, and the resulting adducts were precipitated from the hot solution. Analytical data (Table I) suggest the general formula [M_a(SalH)₂.M_bL₂], where M_a = Ni^{II} or Co^{II} and M_bL₂ = Ca salts of deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline, anthranilic acid and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid. The

colour of the adducts are different from those of the transition metal complexes M(SalH)₂. The adducts are stable under dry condition, having high decomposition temperature.

Infrared spectra show that in salicylaldehyde molecule, due to intra-hydrogen bonding, the $\nu_{C=O}$ (aldehydic) band appears at 1 665 cm⁻¹. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) ligand band (1 282 cm⁻¹) shifts to higher frequency by 40–50 cm⁻¹ on complexation with transition metals, indicating association of phenolic oxygen of the salicylaldehyde. In case of Ni(SalH)₂, which is presumably a trimer, the aldehydic C=O and phenolic C–O both bands split into two and observed at 1 665, 1 636 cm⁻¹ and 1 355, 1 322 cm⁻¹ respectively. Looking into the crystal structure of [Ni(SalH)₂]₃, it is found that half of the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic ones, are bridged oxygens, i.e. one oxygen attached to two Ni^{II} ions. The Co^{II}-salicylaldehyde is also polynuclear, where two aldehydic C=O at 1 655, 1 627 cm⁻¹ and two phenolic C–O at 1 354 and 1 321 cm⁻¹ bands have been observed.

It can be generalised that in metal salicylaldehydes, when they are monomers, the aldehydic C=O and phenolic C–O show only one normal peak at 1 650 and 1 320 cm⁻¹ respectively; whereas in case of polymer with oxygen bridges, both the aldehydic and phenolic frequencies split into two, one at the normal region and the other at a slightly higher frequency. In the polynuclear alkaline earth-transition metal-salicylaldehydes, the aldehydic C=O and phenolic C–O bands have not been observed in their normal range, but invariably higher. This suggests that all these oxygens are bridged ones, bridging the transition metal and most probably the alkaline earth metal.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF
III LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, Decmp. temp.°C)	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			
	N	C	H	Ni/Co
Ni(SalH) ₂ (L) (Green, 270)				
L.Ca(8HQ) ₂ (Green, 300)	4.32 (4.45)	60.20 61.07	3.00 3.49	8.80 9.33
L.Ca(Anth) ₂ (Yellow, 300)	3.80 (4.56)	54.10 54.83	3.00 3.59	8.72 9.58
L.Ca(2H3NA) (Yellow, 300)	–	60.92 (60.44)	3.85 3.35	8.61 8.21
Co(SalH) ₂ (L') (Yellow, 275)				
L'.Ca(8HQ) ₂ (Brown, 900)	5.43 (4.46)	62.80 61.05	3.82 3.49	10.81 9.36
L'.Ca(Anth) ₂ (Green, 300)	3.70 (4.56)	52.99 54.81	3.00 3.58	8.81 9.61
L'.Ca(2H3NA) ₂ (Yellow, 300)	–	61.29 (60.42)	4.15 3.35	9.06 8.24

The magnetic moment of octahedral trimer $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ is 3.35 B.M., whereas the adducts have magnetic moments in the range 3.65–3.8 B.M. These higher magnetic moments values may be due to the change in geometry of the central ion from octahedral to tetrahedral. These metal complexes in absolute ethanolic medium and in presence of partially covalent bonded alkali and alkaline earth metal cations, suffer degradation. It is known that alkali promotes degradation, and quite likely depolymerises these metal complexes into monomers. These monomers *in situ*, behave as a single or double faced bidentate oxygen donor Lewis bases. $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ is also an octahedral tetramer with a magnetic moment of 5.0 B.M. For the corresponding alkaline earth metal adducts, the magnetic moments are in the range 4.52–4.62 B.M. These lower values again suggest a change in geometry of Co^{II} from octahedral to tetrahedral.

The electronic spectrum of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$ shows typical octahedral absorption bands at 450, 600 and 900 nm. The electronic spectra of alkaline earth metal ad-

ducts is different in nature and show one strong band at 640 nm with a hump at 1125 nm, but two other peaks of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$ are missing. This suggests that the octahedral structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ is changed to tetrahedral structure in its alkaline earth metal adducts. $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ shows only one band at 550 nm, which is typical of an octahedral Co^{II} complex. In its alkaline earth metal adducts, this shifts to 600–700 nm. It is very likely that octahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ breaks up into tetrahedral structure in its alkaline earth metal adducts.

The magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of alkaline earth metal adducts reveal depolymerisation of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ to give $\text{M}(\text{SalH})_2$. The bonding between metal salicylaldehyde $\text{M}(\text{SalH})_2$ and alkaline earth metal salts perhaps take place through the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic groups.

Reference

1. A. K. BANERJEE, S. S. PRAKASH and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 515.